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Study on the 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium chloride recovery by electro dialysis method

The 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium chloride ($[O_{mim}]Cl$) is an example of the imidazole based ionic liquid (IL) with a melting point below 100°C. The imidazole based ILs due to their unique physical and chemical properties such as high conductivity, high thermal stability, and ability to solubilize many inorganic and organic compounds can be applied in various industries. The $[O_{mim}]Cl$ can be used for example in the hydrolysis of sucrose, and as catalyst of reactions or in the purification and extraction of biomolecules. However, the very good miscibility of ILs with most solvents caused that their recovery by classical separation techniques can be inefficient. One of the promising methods of the ILs recovery from wastewaters is electro dialysis (ED).

The objective of this work was to evaluate the effectiveness of the $[O_{mim}]Cl$ recovery from aqueous solutions by ED method. The effects of initial $[O_{mim}]Cl$ concentration (0.01 M – 0.15 M), applied voltage (5 - 10 V), and linear flow velocity (1 - 3 cm/s) were investigated. The ED experiments were carried out using an EDR-Z/10-0.8 module (MemBrain, Czech Republic) with an effective membranes area of 320 cm². The membranes used in the experiments were AM-A and AM-C (Ionsep, China). The recovery of the $[O_{mim}]Cl$, the $[O_{mim}]Cl$ molar flux across ion-exchange membranes, the concentration degree, the current efficiency, and the energy consumption were determined.

It was noted that the $[O_{mim}]^+$ flux, and the $[O_{mim}]Cl$ recovery increased with increasing concentration of $[O_{mim}]Cl$. It was found that ED with heterogeneous AM-A and AM-C (Ionsep, China) ion-exchange membranes allows for the recovery of over 85% of $[O_{mim}]Cl$ from aqueous solutions. It can be concluded that, ED can be applied as a promising method of the $[O_{mim}]Cl$ recovery from aqueous solutions.

Keywords: ionic liquids recovery; 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium chloride; electro dialysis

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